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Evaluation of Triticale Bran as Raw Material for Bioethanol Production

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Abstract

The present work addresses the introduction of second generation biofuels from agricultural byproducts generated from low input cereal crops such as triticale. The main purpose was to investigate whether the overall ethanol yield in a triticale dry-mill ethanol plant could be increased by combination of pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis of the bran obtained by fractionation of the grain to separate from starch. Different dilute acid pretreatment conditions were studied using starch-free triticale bran (SFTB) as substrate at a fixed loading of 10 % (dry weight / volume). A statistically experimental design approach, based on previous studies, was used to evaluate the sugars recovery so as to maximize the enzyme digestibility of the pretreated material. The highest overall sugars yield was attained by using 0.1% (w/v) of sulphuric acid at 160 °C for 22.5 minutes. At these conditions, it could be possible to obtain up to 245 L of ethanol per dry ton of SFTB considering hexose and pentose sugars fermentation, which would increase by 14 % the theoretical ethanol yield in a dry-mill ethanol plant.

Keywords: Cereal Bran; Starch; Pretreatment; Enzymatic Hydrolysis; Bioethanol

1. Introduction

Liquid biofuels, such as ethanol, obtained from plant biomass are regarded as an attractive alternative to fuel oil to reduce dependence on foreign oil and diminish CO₂ emissions, the main cause of greenhouse effect. In addition, plant biomass represents the basis for future supply of renewable chemicals and materials [1, 2]. Consequently, South Africa is making efforts to support the production and use of biofuels in the transport sector. Concretely the short-term goal is the replacement of a 2% in the national liquid fuel supply [3].

In order to reach the goals and the envisioned growth of biofuels during the next decades, it is essential to extend the raw materials sources to less expensive crops [4]. Novel dedicated crops with high productivity that are well adapted to the climatic and soils conditions are also critical. Triticale, a hybrid of rye and wheat, has been grown commercially in South Africa for the last two decades. Triticale has a number of potential advantages as a feedstock due to its ability to adapt to stresses and thrive on marginal soils with a lower nitrogen requirement during crop growth [5].

To meet the increasing demand for ethanol it is essential not only to select a suitable raw material but also to use it more efficiently by the utilization of the whole crop, including lignocellulosic residues [6]. Cereal bran is produced as by-product of the milling process and it can account for up to 19% of the grain [7]. Cereal bran usually ends up in the distillers dried grain with solubles (DDGS), that is used as feed supplement limited to cattle due to its high fibre content [8]. The removal of bran from grain during the cortication stage would reduce the fibre content of the DDGS, and thereby increase the protein content up to 60-65% [9]. This will expand the application of DDGS to other livestock and substantially increase its commercial value [10]. Taking advantage of the installed capacities and existing logistics of the present grain-to-ethanol first generation biofuels pathway can be a winning strategy to gradually introduce second generation biofuels. The bran contains a significant amount of sugars [11-15], such as residual starch, cellulose and hemicellulose, which could be converted to ethanol and enhance production efficiency of the production plant.

Among depolymerization processes, those based on enzymatic hydrolysis seem to be promising, due to their specificity and their high potential for improvement by means of biotechnology. The residual starch of the bran can be directly hydrolyzed by amylases. Nonetheless, pretreatment is required to alter the lignocellulose structure in order to improve

enzyme accessibility and increase the yield of fermentable sugars. There are various methods which have been reported in literature that can be used to pretreat lignocellulosic biomass. These are divided into physical and chemical methods or combination of both [16]. Dilute acid hydrolysis is one of the most commonly applied methods among chemical pretreatments [17] since it allows the recovery of a high proportion of hemicellulosic sugars without generating significant concentrations of inhibitors [18]. It has also been shown to increase the rate of enzymatic hydrolysis considerably [19]. Hemicelluloses, mainly as arabinoxylan, accounts for 25 [15] to 44 % [14] of the cereal bran's dry weight. Hence, arabinoxylan recovery can have a positive contribution on the overall process economics of ethanol production when a pentose-fermenting microorganism is available.

Although the feedstocks usually used to study dilute acid pretreatment have been agricultural wastes [20-22], there is relatively little research focused on the pretreatment of cereal bran, and it does not address triticale bran. Previous studies performed on sorghum bran [23], wheat bran [24] and other byproducts originated in a wheat milling plant [25] showed increments in the overall sugars yields by combining pretreatments such as high temperatures with dilute acid.

The main aim of this work was to investigate whether the overall ethanol yield in a triticale dry-mill ethanol plant could be increased by combination of pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis of the bran obtained by fractionation of the grain. The triticale bran was firstly subjected to starch degrading enzymes in order to solubilise the starch fraction. The solid fraction obtained after filtration, designated as starch-free triticale bran (SFTB), was used as substrate for further experiments. The influence of dilute acid pretreatment parameters (temperature, acid loading and residence time) on the enzymatic hydrolysis of the SFTB was studied in order to evaluate its use in a biomass to ethanol process. To assess the effects of these parameters on overall sugar yield, a fractional experimental and surface response technology was employed for experimental design.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw Material

Triticale bran was obtained from SASKO Bakeries, Paarl, South Africa. The triticale bran was sieved in order to obtain the most representative particle size to perform the pretreatment studies. The fraction collected between 425 and 825 μm (~35 % of the triticale bran) was used

in all experiments. The biomass with 9 % moisture content was stored in an air-tight container and was used within 6 months.

2.2. Starch Removal

A low temperature liquefaction and saccharification enzyme preparation, Stargen 001 (Danisco-Genecor, Denmark), with high granular starch hydrolyzing activity was used for starch degradation. Stargen 001 was supplemented with the xylanase preparation Optimash VR (Danisco-Genecor, Denmark) since it has been reported to enhance the starch degradation [7]. The starch hydrolysis of the raw material was performed at a solid-to-water ratio of 1:5. Six 40 g batches were hydrolysed using a 0.5 L Büchi Rotavapor. The hydrolysis was performed in a water solution adjusted at pH 4.2 with 10 N H₂SO₄ [26-27]. Bran slurry supplemented with 0.4 ml of Stargen 001 together with 0.16 ml of Optimash VR was treated at 50 °C with an agitation speed of 150 rpm for 48 hours to ensure maximum starch hydrolysis. The slurry was filtered with Whatman® GF-A and the solid material, denoted as starch-free triticale bran (SFTB), was thoroughly washed with deionized water and air-dried prior to chemical analysis. The liquid was collected for sugar analysis as described below.

2.3. Dilute Acid Pretreatment

Dilute acid batch pretreatment was carried out in tubular reactors as described by Lloyd and Wyman (2005) [28] to minimise mass and energy transfer problems [29]. 0.6 grams of SFTB were soaked overnight in the required acid concentration at a solids concentration of 10% (w/v). Each pretreatment was run in triplicate to produce enough pretreated biomass for analysis of the water insoluble solid (WIS) fraction and for enzymatic hydrolysis.

After quenching the reactors in a cool water bath, the pretreated material was filtered into a WIS fraction and a liquid fraction or prehydrolysate. The WIS fractions were dried for 24 h at 40 °C and analyzed for structural components. These solids were used as substrate in the enzymatic hydrolysis experiments. The liquid fraction after pretreatment was analyzed for sugars and by-products as described below.

2.4. Experimental Design

The dilute acid pretreatment of SFTB was performed using a fractional experimental design as preliminary study to evaluate the parameters that have significant effects on the overall sugar yield. The parameters studied were sulphuric acid concentration (0.1, 0.6 and 1.1 % (w/w),

reaction temperature (120, 140 and 160 °C) and residence time (5, 22.5 and 40 minutes). The experimental error was determined at the centre point (0.6% acid, 140 °C for 22.5 minutes), which was repeated three times. The statistical analysis was performed using the commercial software STATISTICA 7.1 (Statsoft Inc., Tulsa, USA). The significance of effects was estimated by ANOVA.

2.5. Enzymatic Hydrolysis

The washed WIS after pretreatment of SFTB was enzymatically hydrolyzed to determine the effect of the different pretreatment conditions on the enzyme accessibility of the substrate. Enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) was performed in 24 ml glass tubes, each containing 10 ml of 0.05 M sodium citrate buffer (pH 4.8) at 2% (w/v) dry pretreated substrate loading at 50 °C for 72 h. Sodium azide at 0.02% (w/v) was used to prevent microbial contamination. Cellulose-hydrolysing enzymes, Spezyme CP (Genencor-Danisco, Denmark) with a cellulase activity of 65 FPU/ml and a xylanase activity of 310 U/ml, and Novozym 188 (Novozymes A/S, Denmark) with a β -glucosidase activity of 590 IU/ml, were used in all experiments. Enzyme loading of 15 FPU (equivalent to 32.3 mg protein)/g of dry pretreated substrate of Spezyme CP and 15 IU β -glucosidase (equivalent to 2.6 mg protein) /g dry pretreated substrate of β -glucosidase Novozym188 was employed. Samples were withdrawn from the hydrolysis media after 72 hours and sugar content was analysed by HPLC as described below.

2.6. Analytical Methods

Enzyme preparations were subjected to standardized tests to determine protein content and main enzymes activities relevant in the conversion of lignocellulose: cellulase and cellobiase activities. Cellulase and β -glucosidase activities were measured according to methods described by Ghose (1987) [30]. Besides, endo- β -1,4-xylanase activity of Spezyme CP was also assayed by the method described by Bailey et al. (1992) [31]. The protein content was determined by Bicinchoninic acid [BCA]TM assay (BCA-Compat-Able Protein Assay kit, ref. 23229, Pierce, Rockford, IL) using bovine serum albumin as protein standard.

The composition of the triticale bran, starch free triticale bran and solids obtained from the pretreatment were determined using the standard Laboratory Analytical Procedures for biomass analysis provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) (Colorado, USA) [32]. The starch content of the raw material and SFTB were determined by the hydrolysis of the

starch using the Megazyme kit (K-TSTA Lot no. 70302-2, Wicklow, Ireland). The difference between total glucan and starch was assumed to be cellulose.

The liquid fractions after starch degradation and dilute acid pretreatment were analysed for their content of monomeric sugars and soluble oligomeric sugars. The oligosaccharides concentration was determined as the difference in monomers sugar concentration before and after acid hydrolysis of oligosaccharides to monomeric sugars. Sugars (glucose, xylose and arabinose) and by-products (acetic acid, hydroxymethylfurfural and furfural) in the case of the liquid fraction from dilute acid pretreatment were analyzed with an Aminex HPX-87H Ion Exclusion Column equipped with a Cation-H cartridge (Biorad, Johannesburg, RSA). Sugars were measured with a RI detector (Waters 2141, Microsep, Johannesburg, RSA) whereas by-products were analyzed with a UV detector at 220 and 280 nm (Waters 2487, Microsep, Johannesburg, RSA). The column was heated at 65°C and components were separated using 5 mM sulphuric acid as a mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.6 ml/min. Likewise, cellobiose, glucose, xylose and arabinose concentrations after completion of enzymatic hydrolysis tests were measured from the EH media by HPLC as described above. All analytical determinations were performed in duplicate and average results are shown.

3. Results and Discussion

The experimental procedure employed in this study is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The configuration process was divided into two steps. Firstly, the bran was subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis by starch degrading enzymes supplemented with xylanases. The solid obtained (SFTB) was impregnated overnight with dilute sulphuric acid and then pretreated in tubular reactors. The resulting material was separated into a solid residue and a liquid. The solid material was washed with distilled water until a neutral pH was reached and evaluated by enzymatic hydrolysis with cellulases. The sugar yield obtained in each step was used to estimate the theoretical ethanol that could be produced considering an ethanol fermentation yield of 0.44 g/g sugar consumed [33].

3.1. Raw material composition

The composition of the dry raw material is presented in Table 1. Sixty-one percent of the dry raw material consisted of starch, cellulose and arabinoxylan that could be used for ethanol production. The composition of the polymeric fractions of triticale bran was in general

agreement with those reported in literature for wheat and rye bran [7,13, 15, 24], with the starch content being the most variable (from 8 to 32%). The high carbohydrate content, together with its low lignin content (6.6%), makes this feedstock a good candidate for cellulosic ethanol production through appropriate pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation.

3.2. Starch removal

The triticale bran was firstly subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis by means of amylases supplemented with xylanases to remove the initial starch content of about 20%. Table 2 shows the carbohydrate composition of the liquid and solid fractions obtained from the bran after starch removal. Compared with the composition of the original bran (Table 1), the percentage of starch in the solid was decreased to 6.4%, whereas the cellulose content increased from 16.8 to 24.6%. The main carbohydrate, arabinoxylan, comprised 36.3 % of the SFTB, representing a 12.6% more than in the original bran. The carbohydrate content was in the range reported for destarched wheat bran [11-12]. The glucose yield was 16 g/100 g of original bran, which corresponded to 71.3% of the theoretical yield based on the glucose from the initial starch in the triticale bran (22.44 g/100 g of original bran). If all this glucose was fermented, 89 L of ethanol per dry ton of bran could be theoretically produced. Considering the pentose released due to the xylanase activity, the amount of ethanol per dry ton of bran could be increased up to 116 L. Hence, the starch removal step allowed the recovery of not only the glucose from starch but also some of the hemicellulosic sugars. Besides, it provided a solid fraction enriched in cellulose and hemicellulose (67.3% of the dry weight) more suitable for dilute acid pretreatment.

3.3. Dilute acid pretreatment

Pretreatment experiments were carried out in small tubular reactors which facilitate material balance closure for varying reaction conditions [29]. A substrate loading of 10% (dry weight/volume) of the solid fraction, SFTB, was subjected to dilute acid pretreatment under different process parameters: temperature (120–160 °C), sulphuric acid concentration (0.1–1.1 %, w/w) and residence time (5-40 minutes). Pretreatment temperature was limited to 160 °C by thermal decomposition characteristics of triticale bran as determined by thermal gravimetric analysis (data not shown). The chosen range of catalyst concentration was based on preliminary studies where a notable reduction in solid recoveries was observed at temperatures and acid concentration higher than 160 °C and 1.5% (w/w), respectively.

The effect of these parameters was evaluated in terms of sugar recovery during pretreatment and cellulose susceptibility of the solid fraction to enzymatic hydrolysis. These two responses were used to assess the overall sugar yield, considering both pretreatment and enzymatic steps.

3.3.1. Effect of dilute acid pretreatment in the composition of SFTB

The solid recovery, defined as the solids remaining after pretreatment divided by original oven-dried weight and the carbohydrate composition of the different fractions obtained after pretreatment at different conditions are given in Table 3. The solids recovery decreased at higher temperatures for example from 72.8 % at 120 °C to 34.7 % when the applied temperature was 160 °C.

Hemicellulose content is an important indicator of the effectiveness of dilute acid pretreatment [34], being the arabinoxylan present at high levels in cereal bran. Arabinose comprised the largest portion of arabinoxylan in the SFTB (about 59 %, Table 2) and it has been shown to be the least stable sugar during the pretreatment [35]. Arabinose was already solubilised at the lowest temperature reaching solubilisations of up to 57 % of initial content (120 °C, 1.1% acid for 22.5 minutes). This could be due to the arabinoxylan structure, where the arabinose is present as side chain residues, facilitating the hydrolysis of the glucosidic bonds during the pretreatment. The arabinose recovered in the solid residue ranged from 0 to 9.2 g/100 g SFTB (dry weight) (Table 3). In the case of xylose, present in the arabinoxylan backbone, the lowest value in the solids (1.2 g/100 g SFTB, dw) was obtained at the most severe conditions (160 °C, 1.1% acid for 40 minutes), corresponding with a solubilisation of 75.4%.

Glucan recovered on the pretreated solids varied between 13.3 g/100 g SFTB (160 °C, 1.1% acid for 40 minutes) and 26.1 g/100 g SFTB (120 °C, 0.1% acid for 5 minutes) (Table 3).

Temperatures higher than 120 °C have been shown to solubilise starch [21]. At this temperature, the glucose yield in the liquid reached values between 4.8 and 6.9 g/100 g SFTB. This last value corresponded approximately with the amount of glucose from the residual starch (7.0 g/100 g SFTB).

Furfural and HMF, degradation products from pentoses and hexoses respectively, were also quantified together with acetic acid since they are considered as the main inhibitors for the downstream processing. The maximum concentration of furfural, HMF and acetic acid detected

after SFTB pretreatment, under the harsher conditions (160 °C, 1.1% (w/v) acid concentration for 40 minutes) were 0.41, 0.13 and 0.35 g/l, respectively (data not shown). These amounts have been found to be below the inhibitory level for *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (1.2, 0.3 and 6 g/l for furfural, HMF and acetic acid, respectively) [36].

3.3.2. Enzymatic hydrolysis of pretreated SFTB

The effect of different pretreatment conditions on cellulose digestibility was assessed by enzymatic hydrolysis of the solid fraction of pretreated SFTB (WIS fraction). The enzymatic hydrolysis yields were expressed as percentage of glucose released in relation to potential glucose in each WIS fraction after 72 h (Table 3).

Regression analysis was performed to fit the response function with the experimental data. The statistical significance of the effect of temperature, acid concentration and residence time on enzymatic hydrolysis yield was determined by ANOVA, which revealed that the regression was statistically significant at a 95% confidence level in the case of temperature. In addition, the model presented a high determination coefficient ($R^2 = 0.996$; $R^2_{\text{adjusted}} = 0.985$), explaining 98.5% of the variability in the enzymatic hydrolysis yield observed. The results are represented in a standardized Pareto chart (Fig. 2A) where it can be observed that, for the range investigated, the temperature was the only quantity that showed a positive significant linear effect on the enzymatic hydrolysis yield.

The model was refined according to the ANOVA results in Equation (1) which describes the correlation between the temperature and the enzymatic hydrolysis yield of the WIS:

$$(1) \text{ EH yield} = 52.8 + 33.6T - 15.5T^2$$

The response surface graph for the enzymatic hydrolysis yield using Eq. 1 is shown in Figure 2B. The maximal enzymatic hydrolysis yield was predicted at temperatures higher than 140 °C. When the pretreatment was performed at 120 and 140 °C the enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) yields were just slightly higher compared with non pretreated SFTB (about 15%, data not shown). The enzymatic hydrolysis yield rose up from 22 % when pretreatment was carried out at lower temperature (120 °C) up to 100% at 160 °C. This trend correlated with the hemicellulose removal from the solid observed (Table 3), which has been shown to substantially increase the enzymatic hydrolysis yield [37].

3.3.3. Overall sugars yield

An effective pretreatment should disrupt the lignocellulose structure to increase the accessibility of the enzymes and therefore, the enzymatic hydrolysis yield. However, in establishing optimum pretreatment conditions it is also valuable to recover a high concentration of sugars, considering also the sugars solubilised during pretreatment. Results of the glucose yield from pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis are shown in Fig. 3. The lowest yields of glucose in the enzymatic hydrolysis step, 5.2-7.9 g/100 g SFTB, were obtained for the pretreatments carried out at 120 °C. Nonetheless, these values were higher than those reached for the untreated SFTB (4 g/100 g SFTB). The enzymatic glucose yield rose up to 19.9 g/100 g SFTB after pretreatment at 160 °C, 0.1% sulphuric acid for 22.5 minutes. At these conditions, the overall glucose yield was also maximum, 26 g/100 g SFTB, higher than those reported on destarched wheat bran when the pretreatment was performed at 160 °C, 0.2% sulphuric acid for 20 minutes [24]. Considering the overall glucose yield obtained under these conditions, a potential ethanol of 145 L per dry ton of SFTB could theoretically be obtained.

Since the arabinoxylan is the major component in the hemicellulose structure of cereal bran, its recovery could contribute positively in the final ethanol yield when an industrial pentose-fermenting microorganism is developed. Figure 4 showed the yield of hemicellulosic sugars (xylose and arabinose) during pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis compared with the untreated SFTB. Pretreatment performed at 160 °C, 0.1% (w/v) acid concentration for 22.5 minutes provided the highest hemicellulosic sugars yield after pretreatment (15.7 g/100 g SFTB). At the same pretreatment conditions, the highest overall yield of hemicellulosic sugars, 18.0 g/100 g SFTB (49.2 % of theoretical), was obtained. If these sugars were cofermented together with the glucose, a potential ethanol of 245 L of ethanol per dry ton SFTB could be reached.

4. Conclusions

Due to the fact that enzymatic hydrolysis is not efficient enough to release monomeric sugars from the carbohydrates present in the starch free triticale bran, the dilute acid pretreatment was needed to make the lignocellulose structure more digestible. Furthermore, residual starch on the cereal bran required an additional processing step in order to obtain a more homogeneous substrate for further pretreatment as well as to recover fermentable sugars.

Temperatures higher than 140 °C were required in order to enhance cellulose accessibility by dilute acid pretreatment. Pretreatments carried out at 160 °C produced residues with higher

digestibility in comparison to the non pretreated SFTB. The maximum overall sugar yield, 44 g/100 g SFTB, considering the pretreatment step (sugars solubilised in the liquid fraction) and the enzymatic hydrolysis, was obtained when the pretreatment was performed at 160 °C, 0.1% (w/v) acid concentration for 22.5 minutes. The results obtained herein provide insight into the factors controlling dilute acid performance of triticale bran and can be considered as starting point for scaling up to larger reactors.

In conclusion triticale bran is an interesting raw material for increasing the ethanol yield in a dry-mill cereal plant. Considering an average ethanol yield of 365.1 L per ton in a dry milling plant from barley or rye [38], and a 20% content of bran in the grain, a total increase of 30 L and 50 L ethanol per ton of the initial grain (corresponding with 8.2% and 13.7%) could be reached with and without pentose-fermenting yeast respectively. Nevertheless, the yields achieved with the considered pretreatment conditions are still low for an industrial ethanol process, and further investigations are necessary to achieve an economical process.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1: Experimental layout for assessment of the process configuration.

Figure 2: (A) Standardized Pareto chart for enzymatic hydrolysis yield (%). Standardized effects are calculated by dividing the effect by its standard error. (B) Estimated response surface for enzymatic hydrolysis yield showing the influence of temperature and sulphuric acid concentration for a residence time of 22.5 minutes.

Figure 3: Yield of glucose (g/100 g SFTB) in pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, and overall as function of pretreated conditions (■, pretreatment; □, enzymatic hydrolysis) in comparison with the enzymatic hydrolysis yield (g/100 g SFTB) of the untreated SFTB.

Figure 4: Yield of hemicellulosic sugars (g/100 g SFTB) in pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, and overall as function of pretreated conditions (■, pretreatment; □, enzymatic hydrolysis) in comparison with the enzymatic hydrolysis yield (g/100 g SFTB) of the untreated SFTB.

Tables

Table 1. Composition of triticale bran (TB).

Component	% dw
Extractives	17.6 ± 1.6
Carbohydrates	
Starch	20.4 ± 2.1
Cellulose	16.8 ± 1.3
Xylan	13.4 ± 0.5
Arabinan	10.3 ± 0.4
Acid Insoluble Lignin	6.6 ± 0.3
Ash	4.8 ± 0.2

Mean values and standard deviation of five determinations

Table 2. Carbohydrates composition of triticale bran after treatment with amylases supplemented with xylanases.

Treatment				Carbohydrates						
Starch Degradation				Solid Fraction: Starch-Free Triticale Bran (SFTB)				Liquid Fraction		
				(% dry weight)				(g/100 g raw material)		
Temperature	Catalyst	Time	Solid Recovery (%)	Residual starch	Glucan	Xylan	Arabinan	Glucose	Xylose	Arabinose
50 °C	Amylases	48 h	54.5 ± 2.3	6.4 ± 0.7 (3.5)	31.0 ± 1.8 (17.1)	14.9 ± 0.7 (8.2)	21.4 ± 1.4 (11.8)	16.0 ± 1.2	4.4 ± 1.1	0.5 ± 0.1

The data in brackets are expressed as a percentage based on dry weight of raw material.

Table 3. Solid recovery (%), carbohydrate composition of the prehydrolyzate and water insoluble solids (WIS) and enzymatic hydrolysis yield (%) obtained after dilute acid pretreatment of SFTB.

Pretreatment conditions				Solid Recovery (%)	Carbohydrates						EH Yield* (%)
Run	Temp (°C)	H ₂ SO ₄ % (w/v)	Time (min)		WIS Fraction % dw (g/ 100 g SFTB)			Prehydrolyzate yield (g/ 100 g SFTB)			
					Glucans	Xylans	Arabinans	Glucose	Xylose	Arabinose	
1		0.1	5	72.8	35.9 (26.1)	11.4 (8.3)	12.7 (9.2)	4.8	2.6	2.4	25.1
2	120	0.6	40	65.7	32.4 (21.3)	11.3 (7.4)	11.6 (7.6)	6.9	4.0	2.8	22.0
3		1.1	22.5	57.8	30.2 (17.5)	10.4 (6.0)	9.2 (5.3)	5.5	3.1	2.8	41.3
4		0.1	40	61.2	34.6 (21.2)	9.3 (5.7)	9.9 (6.1)	8.0	4.8	4.4	34.9
5	140	0.6	22.5	61.2	34.9 (21.3)	9.1 (5.6)	9.4 (5.8)	8.3	5.6	5.0	29.9
6		1.1	5	65.6	33.0 (21.6)	9.7 (6.4)	12.2 (8.0)	8.3	4.3	3.7	31.7
7		0.1	22.5	43.5	41.7 (18.1)	4.7 (2.0)	nd	6.1	7.7	8.0	100.0
8	160	0.6	5	46.8	43.3 (20.3)	4.5 (2.1)	nd	5.2	6.1	6.1	89.3
9		1.1	40	34.7	38.4 (13.3)	3.4 (1.2)	nd	5.9	6.0	6.0	100.0

The data in brackets are expressed as a percentage based on dry weight of SFTB.

nd: not detected

* Enzymatic hydrolysis yield based on potential glucose in WIS

Figures

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